

Checklist - Defect Mapping

Category	Item	Defect ID
General	Are all the changes relevant?	WHOLEWORDMISSING
	Do the classes and methods fulfill their purpose?	WHOLEWORDMISSING MATCH_END_NOT_SET
	Are messages and texts for the user correct?	TYPO_PATH TYPO_MATCH
Classes	Are all assignments of attributes correct?	LOADINFO_NOT_SET SET_NO_WORD_SEP_WRONG
	Are the classes implemented correctly? e.g., do they correctly implement inheritance or are they protected against unintentional access to their data?	
Methods	Do the methods always return a valid value?	MATCH_END_NOT_SET
	Do the methods check parameters for validity (if needed)?	MISSING_CHECK_START MISSING_CHECK_END
	Are all parameters used?	WRONG_PATH_ASSIGNMENT LOADINFO_NOT_SET
Arguments	Are the correct arguments used in all method calls?	CANCELLABLE_WRONG WRONG_PROPERTY FROM_TO_SWAP FROM_TO_SWITCHED_RENAME1
Variables	Are variables, counters and accumulators initialized properly and, Are all declared variables being used?	MISSING_LATCH_DECREMENT LOADINFO_NOT_SET SET_NO_WORD_SEP_WRONG
If-Then Statements	Do the if-else statements fit the intended purpose?	IS_END_WORD_WRONG_RESULT SET_NO_WORD_SEP_WRONG
	Are all edge-cases handled?	
Loops	Do the loops end under all possible conditions?	DANGEROUS_RECURSION
	Are the break and continue statements used properly?	MISSING_CONTINUE
Recursion	Does the recursion terminate properly?	DANGEROUS_RECURSION
Errors	Are the exceptions handled correctly?	INTERRUPTED_EXCEPTION

Final check	Are all the changes consistent with each other?	WHOLEWORDMISSING
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